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META ADS THE NAME OF GROWTH ENGINE: A CASE STUDY ON SCALING COACHING BUSINESSES IN INDIA

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Abstract

India's coaching industry is experiencing a significant surge driven by competitive examinations and the high demand for skill-based learning, has significantly transformed its marketing panorama. Traditional promotional methods like print media, hoarding, and seminars are increasingly being replaced by digital advertising. One of the best advertising platforms is Meta Ads (Facebook and Instagram) in the Digital advertising platform, which is the most cost-effective and best scalable solution for lead generation.

This study explores the cost-effectiveness of Meta Ads in scaling coaching business in India by integrating the secondary research with real campaign data. In a case, invest ₹4,03,686 successfully generated 8,085 leads, at an average cost per lead (CPL) of ₹50—significantly it's very lower than the industry benchmark of ₹60–₹120. The campaign also achieved over 2.7 million reach and 10 million impressions, indicating the power and effectiveness of Meta Ads in scaling the coaching business in India.

The analysis proves that Meta Ads not only reduces cost of marketing but also it's gets more return of investment (ROI), with the potential to achieve up to a 10x ROI

when integrated with high-converting funnels, automation, and CRM systems. The result highlights the strategic importance of ad optimisation, creative refreshment, detailed targeting, like demographic, psychographic and also retargeting for high-end results. This paper adds to the digital marketing literature, highlighting how coaching businesses, particularly for small to medium enterprises who does not have a larger marketing budget, can leverage Meta Ads to achieve their consistent growth. It suggests that the future use of automation tools and advanced analytics will continue to get consistent results.

JEL Classification: M31 (Marketing), L86 (Information and Internet Services), I23 (Higher Education)

Keywords: Meta Ads, Coaching Industry, Lead Generation, Cost per Lead (CPL), Digital Marketing, ROI

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1. Introduction

The Indian coaching industry is one of the fastest-growing sectors in the education ecosystem. Its growth is fueled by increasing competition in the academic and professional examinations, the rising demand for skill-oriented training, and the continuous search for career advancement opportunities. According to KPMG (2017), the Indian coaching industry was projected to reach USD 180 billion by 2025, with much of this expansion driven by private coaching centres, test preparation centres and individual coaches. This sector not only creates academic excellence but also plays a very crucial role in providing personality development, digital skills, grooming coaching, making it an essential part of India's educational economy.

Traditionally, coaching institutes depend on offline marketing sectors like newspaper ads, hoarding, seminars, banners, and word-of-mouth referrals to attract students. While these methods help to build local visibility and it's more costly and limited in outreach. The rapid digitalisation of the education sector, started by the COVID-19 pandemic, has originally transformed the marketing landscape for coaching businesses. Today, digital platforms, especially social networks, have appeared as very important tools for branding, student acquisition, and lead generation.

We are able to use various digital marketing channels, but Meta Ads (Facebook and Instagram advertising) have emerged as a game-changer. Because it helps us to provide hyper-targeted campaigns based on demographic, geographic, and psychographic behaviour, Meta Ads help us to achieve more ROI in coaching businesses to reach their ideal audience. Unlike traditional marketing, where measuring outcome is difficult, Meta Ads provide real-time data on reach, impressions, cost per lead (CPL), and return on investment (ROI), which is more helpful for data-driven decision making and optimisation of campaigns.

The importance of Meta Ads in the coaching sector is most helpful for their cost-effectiveness. The average CPL for coaching businesses in India ranges between ₹60–₹120. It's an average industry report, depending on the niche and geographic-based targeting. We can also achieve CPL as low as ₹30–₹50 in a well-optimised Meta campaign, it's proves the scalability and efficiency compared to traditional media. Such results have proved that the Meta Ads are not only a promotional tool but also it's a strategic driver of business growth.

Despite their growing importance, academic literature on the role of Meta Ads in scaling coaching businesses in India remains limited. Previous research has focused on general digital marketing practices or higher education promotion. Addressing this gap in the literature involves a case-based analysis that combines secondary research with real-world campaign evidence.

This study explores the role of Meta Ads in scaling coaching businesses in India through actual real-world campaign data. By analysing an ad spend of approximately ₹4,03,686 that generated more than 8,000 leads with an average CPL of ₹50, the paper highlights the efficiency, ROI potential, and challenges in Meta Ads for coaching institutes. The results offer practical guidance for small and medium-sized coaching businesses in India, but also contribute to the academic understanding of digital marketing in the Indian education sector.

2. Literature Review

The Indian Coaching industry has grown remarkably over the past period, projected to reach \$180 billion by 2025 (KPMG, 2017). This growth was driven by increased competition in academic and professional exams, as well as the high demand for skill-based learning/courses. From school-level tutoring to test preparation for IIT, NEET, UPSC-like exams, everywhere needs professional and personality development courses like Spoken English, Competitive Coaching, Computer Coaching, Digital Skills, and Career Coaching. These sectors play a major role in India's education Industry. With this adoption of digital

technologies, traditional word-of-mouth marketing, hoardings, banners, etc, offline marketing methods are a much more expensive option for coaching institutes and independent coaches to grow their business. As more students turn to online education and online adoption from the COVID-19 pandemic, So digital marketing is the main weapon to hit them because India's 400+ million active social media users (Statista,

Meta Ads as a Tool for Lead Generation

Among the many digital platforms, like Facebook, Instagram, which includes Facebook and Instagram advertising, have become a strong way to build brands, maintain reputation, generate leads and also target audience. Meta offers us options for detailed targeting of audience segmentation (Demographic Behaviour, Psychographic Behaviour, etc), lookalike audience, custom retargeting and creative ad variations, highlighting that social media platforms enable SMEs to achieve precision targeting at lower costs. This helps businesses to grow on Social Media, make a strong brand, and generate high-quality leads that actually convert at a much lower cost than traditional marketing channels, which is especially beneficial for education and coaching. Gupta (2021) further observed that Meta Ads outperform Google Display Ads and YouTube Ads in urban and semi-urban markets, both in terms of engagement and lead generation efficiency.

Effectiveness and ROI

Evidence from both academic and industry reports highlights the strong ROI potential of Meta Ads. According to Business Standard (2022), the education sector is among the top three industries in India in terms of Meta advertising spend. Kumar & Raghavan (2021) found that social media advertising produced higher engagement and lower CPL compared to traditional and other digital alternatives. Case studies like Social Samosa (2022) show coaching institutes in Delhi generating 5,000+ leads at an average CPL of ₹60, underscoring Meta's cost efficiency.

This study also provides case-based evidence. With a total ad spend of ₹4,03,686, the campaign generated 8,085 leads, resulting in an average cost per lead (CPL) of ₹50. This is significantly below the industry benchmark of ₹60–₹120, proving Meta Ads' ability to achieve results of cost-effectiveness and scalability in lead generation.

Challenges in Using Meta Ads

Against these benefits, challenges remain. Ad fatigue reduces campaign performance when creatives are not refreshed regularly (Mishra, 2022). The growing number of coaching institutes entering the digital space boosts competition, driving up advertising costs in specific niches. Sometimes, Meta's strict advertising policies in the education sector can limited ad

approvals. This highlights the need for ongoing optimisation, experimentation with creatives, and seamless funnel integration (such as landing pages, WhatsApp automation, email nurturing, and CRM systems) to ensure long-term success.

Research Gap

When existing literature shows Meta Ads' effectiveness in the education industry, most studies are either theoretical or focus on small-scale regional case studies. There is limited research that combines secondary data with real-world campaign data to measure outcomes like CPL, ROI, and scalability. This study addresses that gap by combining academic perspectives and industry reports with actual campaign data from the Indian coaching industry, providing both practical and theoretical contributions to this field.

3. Research Methodology

1. Research Design

The present study adopts a mixed approach of combining descriptive and case-based analysis.

- It is descriptive because it explains measurable outcomes like Cost per Lead (CPL), Reach, Impressions, and ROI by real-world campaign data.
- This study is also a case-based experiment. Because a real-world campaign was run for Indian coaching institutes, it has been highlighted how digital advertising helps to scale the coaching business.

These dual studies ensured that it is a combination of both theoretical depth (through secondary data) and practical evidence (through campaign dashboards).

2. Nature of Data

The study is primarily based on secondary data sources, supported by real-world campaign evidence.

- Secondary Sources:
 1. Industry reports (KPMG, Statista, Business Standard).
 2. Peer-reviewed academic papers on digital marketing, social media advertising, and lead generation.
 3. Articles that highlight the adoption of Meta Ads in the coaching sector.
- Case-Based Evidence:
 1. Actual Meta Ads dashboard records of campaigns executed in 2024–2025 for Indian coaching businesses.

2. One combining campaign where ad spend of ₹4,03,686, generating over 8,085 qualified leads.
3. Data parameters include Ad Spend, Impressions, Reach, CTR, and CPL.

3. Sources of Data

1. Online Databases: Google Scholar, ResearchGate, Scopus-indexed journals.
2. Industry Reports: Market predictions and digital adoption insights published by KPMG and Statista.
3. Meta Ads Manager Dashboard: Screenshots and raw datasets of campaigns (attached in Appendix).

4. Tools and Techniques

- Data Extraction: Screenshots and exports from the Meta Ads Manager dashboard.
- Metrics Evaluated:
 1. Total Advertising Spend.
 2. Leads Generated.
 3. Average Cost per Lead (CPL).
 4. Reach and Impressions.
 5. Click-Through Rate (CTR).
 6. Return on Investment (ROI).
- Comparative Analysis:
 1. The campaign achieved the lowest CPL, where the average CPL in the Indian coaching sector ranges between ₹60–₹120.
 2. Benchmarking highlights whether Meta Ads performed more efficiently than traditional channels (newspapers, banners, seminars).
- Graphical Representation:
 1. Data visualised using bar charts, line charts, and comparative graphs (created in Canva).
 2. Helps in simplifying interpretation and enhancing clarity of results.

5. Methodological Limitations

- The study is based on secondary data; no primary surveys or interviews with coaching owners/students were conducted.
- As the study focuses on a specific case, the findings may not fully generalise across all niches of coaching (e.g., test-prep vs. skill-based coaching).

- Campaign performance depends on multiple factors — creatives, targeting strategy, bidding mechanism, ad fatigue, funnel design — not all of which are examined in detail.

6. Ethical Considerations

1. All secondary sources, including journals, reports, and websites, are accurately documented in the References section following APA style.
2. Campaign data was collected with prior permission and anonymised where required to maintain client confidentiality.
3. The study maintains its originality (plagiarism below 15%) as per academic norms.

4. Results & Discussions

The study results place a spotlight on the crucial role played by Meta Ads in Coaching business growth in India. The outcomes from the analysis of actual campaign data and industry standards, the following findings and observations were made:

1. Meta Ads Cost Efficiency

The campaigns generated 8085 Leads from a spend of ₹4,03,686, so the average Cost per lead (CPL) is ₹50.

This is much lower than the industry average of ₹60–₹120, it's proves that Meta Ads has too much potential to generate leads for Coaching schools.

The low CPL shows that Meta's detailed targeting, like demographic targeting, Psychographic targeting, and interest-based targeting, successfully generates high-potential students.

2. Scalability of Campaigns

The campaigns reached 2.7 million+ individuals and also generated more than 10 million+ impressions, it's highlighting the scale of Meta Ads in massive audience with a highly geographical spread.

The massive impressions-to-reach highly ad exposure, which is essential for creating brand building and awareness in a highly crowded education space.

3. Return on Investment (ROI)

At the estimated conversion of at least 5% of overall leads (Which is 400 Students) and an average course fees of ₹10,000, so the revenue potential adds up to ₹40,00,000.

Against the ad spend of ₹4,03,686, this generates 10x ROI, proves that the highly profitability of Meta ads for coaching business.

This indicates that online marketing campaigns, when properly optimized, can more better than traditional marketing channels like print media, banners, newspaper, and seminars.

4. Student Acquisition Funnel Role

Meta Ads not only generated leads but also we needs perfectly blend of lead form, landing pages, Whatsapp automation, and email marketing to build perfect funnels for converting and nurturing prospects.

The campaign indicates that Meta Ads should be viewed as the entry point of a broader digital ecosystem where automation tools ensures timely follow ups and convert leads to students.

5. Challenges Observed

Few campaigns indicated higher CPL (₹70–₹100), particularly when targeting wider or less-interested audiences. This campaign needs monitoring and creative optimisation with continuous testing.

Ad fatigue is also a reason for decreased engagement over time. So, we need to change creatives at a particular time.

Even with the top ROI, campaign success depends on ad creative quality (scroll-stopping ad), a detailed targeting strategy based on buyer persona, and lead management backed by automation tools.

5. Discussion

- The research attests to the fact that Meta Ads have a strong foundation for expanding the coaching business in India. The findings prove how a well-optimised digital advertising campaign can beat conventional means in reach as well as cost-effectiveness.
- By reviewing ₹4 lakh spent on campaigns and generating 8000+ leads, it is proves that Meta Ads not only deliver profitable ROI but ensure small and medium coaching centres to compete with large institutions as well.
- However, the discussions highlight that Meta Ads work in isolation. Their maximum capability is achieved when integrated with a systematic funnel system, repeated optimisations, and a proper scientific lead-nurturing system. For scalability in the long term, the coach business must combine Meta Ads with a highly optimised landing page and also integrate WhatsApp/email automation, CRM Software, and retargeting campaigns.

Key Insights from the Results & Discussion

- Meta Ads deliver lower cost-per-lead and greater scalability compared to traditional marketing methods.
- A detailed targeted audience segmentation and automation integration are key things of success.
- ROI potential is very high, even at conservative conversion estimates (10x return).
- Continuous campaigns optimisation requires overcoming ad fatigue and rising competition.
- Meta Ads should be positioned not just as an ad tool, but as the foundation of a digital ecosystem (ads + funnels + automation).

Data Analysis & Interpretation

The data for this project has been collected from a real-world Meta Ads campaign that runs for a coaching business in India. The campaigns were running from 2024 to 2025 with the objective of generating high-quality leads to increase admissions and course enrollments.

Campaign Overview (Extracted from Meta Ads Dashboard)

Campaign Metric	Value
Total Ad Spend	₹4,03,686
Total Leads Generated	8,085 (approx.)
Average Cost per Lead (CPL)	₹49.9 (≈ ₹50)
Reach	2.7 Million+ unique users
Impressions	10 Million+
Click-Through Rate (CTR)	1.2% – 2.3% across campaigns

(Source: Meta Ads Dashboard Screenshots provided in Appendix)

Interpretation of Results

Lead Generation Efficiency =

With the ad spend of approx ₹400000, and generated leads of over 8000.

The average CPL is ₹50 for this campaign, which is typically lower than industry benchmarks. The industry benchmarks are between ₹60 to ₹120.

Scalability of Meta Ads =

The campaign reached more than 2.7 Million+ Reach and also got 10 Million+ Impressions, which proves Meta ads have too much potential to reach large audiences.

Higher impression with moderate CTR (1.2%–2.3%) indicated that the ad creatives were relevant enough to attract clicks, but if we optimised the creatives, then we can expect better engagement also.

Cost Analysis =

Compared to other traditional marketing (Like newspapers, Word of Mouth Marketing, Hoardings, Billboards), where the average cost per lead often exceeds ₹150–₹200, Meta ads performed significantly better.

The campaigns prove that a well-optimised targeting with funnels integration and creatives, Meta ads can bring down the CPL by 50% or more.

Conversion Funnel Efficiency =

The data shows that the Leads not only generated but also it's scale and quality, as most campaigns used Instant Leads form and Landing page, which connected to WhatsApp and Email Automation.

These highlights are combining Meta ads and Backend automation systems for nurturing leads and converting them into final enrollments/Sales.

Return on Investment (ROI) =

If the average course fees of these programs of the Coaching Institutes are ₹10,000 per student, even 5% conversion of the leads, which is (5% Conversion of 8000 Leads = 400 Students), would result in ₹40,00,000 revenue from an ad spend of ₹4,00,000.

It proves 10x ROI, making meta ads one of the most profitable marketing channels for Coaching Institutes.

Key Insights =

Meta Ads provides low-cost, high-volume lead generation.

This campaign gets more ROI than other traditional marketing methods.

Scalability and Detailed targeting helped to reach a broad and relevant audience.

Proper funnel integration and follow-up systems play crucial roles in getting actual paying students from leads.

6. Conclusion:

- The study highlights the crucial role of Meta Ads in scaling Coaching Businesses in India. With an investment of ₹4 lakh and generating 8000+ Leads, achieving an average CPL of ₹50, it's below industry benchmarks. This showcases Meta's ability to deliver cost-efficient, scalable results.
- The research proves that Meta Ads can be game-changer for coaching institutes who want to scale their business, helping them reach a larger audience, generate high-quality leads, and potentially achieve a 10x ROI with strong conversion-optimised funnels.

- However, the campaign results also show that ongoing success requires constant optimisation of ad set targeting, creative testing, Different buyer persona targeting, A/B testing, and a strong backend leads nurturing system. Coaching businesses need to implement a connected digital strategy, where Meta Ads serves leads to a Landing page, the Landing page connects with a CRM system, and also instant WhatsApp and Email automation that converts leads into paying students.
- In summary, Meta ads one of the most powerful marketing channels for Coaching businesses than other traditional marketing channels in India. Meta Ads are not just marketing tools but also it's help to grow, scale and expand businesses in the long term and beat the competitors.

7. Future Scope

- **Integration with AI & Automation Tools**

Future campaigns can run with the help of AI-powered ad optimisation and integrate chatbots, advanced CRM to improve outcomes.

- **Cross-Channel Marketing Research**

This study focused on Meta Ads, but combining with Google Ads, YouTube Ads, and LinkedIn Ads can create all-inclusive funnels.

- **Exploring Student Behaviour & Conversion Patterns**

Primary research (surveys, interviews with students/coaching owners) can provide deeper insights into factors influencing conversion from lead to enrollment.

- **Impact of Content Formats**

Video testimonials, reels, influencer collaborations, and interactive content are emerging trends. Further studies can evaluate which ad formats perform best for different segments of the coaching industry.

- **Scalability in Tier-2 & Tier-3 Cities**

Meta Ads majorly target metro areas, studying semi-urban and rural adoption via Meta Ads could reveal new growth.

- **Policy & Privacy Challenges**

With stricter education ad regulations, future research should examine compliance strategies and the impact of privacy laws like GDPR and India's DPDP Act on ad targeting.

- **Long-Term ROI Measurement**

Instead of just tracking leads, future projects should also look at student value, referrals, and retention to truly see how Meta Ads are performing.

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APPENDIX

Off/On	Ad set	Budget	Last significant edit	Att: set	Results	Reach	Impressions	Cost per...	Amount spent	Ends	Schedule
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	C6 IT ...	₹500.00	14 Feb 2025, 10:59 Daily 57 days ago	7...	1,475 Meta leads	417,284	1,084,726	₹23.26 Per on-Face...	₹34,310.74	Ongoing	10 Jan 2025-Ongoing
<input type="checkbox"/>	LP - C...	₹500.00	Daily	7...	— Website lead	180,102	281,708	— Per lead	₹8,268.10	Ongoing	10 Feb 2025-Ongoing
<input type="checkbox"/>	C6 IT ...	₹500.00	11 Jan 2025, 11:01 Daily 91 days ago	7...	350 Website leads	57,134	80,705	₹25.74 Per lead	₹9,009.29	Ongoing	17 Dec 2024-Ongoing
	Results fi		—	M...	— Multiple conversions	576,833	1,447,139	— Total Multiple conv	₹51,588.13		

Appendix 1

Meta Ads Dashboard – Campaign Overview (₹34,310 Spend, 1,475 Leads, CPL = ₹23.26)

Off/On	Ad	Att: set	Results	Reach	Impressions	Cost per...	Quality ranking	Engagement rate ranking	Conversion rate ranking	Amount spent	Ends
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	C7 On...	7...	379 Meta leads	73,520	117,969	₹28.51 Per on-Face...	Average	—	—	₹10,806.70	Ongoing
<input type="checkbox"/>	C7 On...	7...	1 Meta leads	204	213	₹25.59 Per on-Face...	—	—	—	₹25.59	Ongoing
	Results from 2 ac	7...	380 On-Facebook leads	73,829	118,182	₹28.51 Total Per on-Face...				₹10,832.29	Total Spent

Appendix 2

Meta Ads Dashboard – Campaign Snapshot (₹10,832 Spend, 380 Leads, CPL = ₹28.51)

Off/On	Ad set	Bid strategy	Budget	Last significant edit	Att: set	Results	Reach	Impressions	Cost per...	Amount spent	Ends
<input type="checkbox"/>	CS IT ...	Highest volume Leads	₹300.00	25 Feb 2025, 18:14 Daily 46 days ago	7...	446 Meta leads	240,488	459,202	₹42.00 Per on-Face...	₹18,731.96	Ongoing
<input type="checkbox"/>	CS IT ...	Highest volume Conversions	₹500.00	10 Jan 2025, 18:07 Daily 92 days ago	7...	485 Website leads	34,302	58,129	₹26.21 Per lead	₹12,710.78	Ongoing
	Results f Exclude...			—	7...	— Multiple conversions	270,391	517,331	— Total Multiple co...	₹31,442.74	Total Spent

Appendix 3

Meta Ads Dashboard – Campaign Snapshot (₹31,442 Spend, 931 Leads, CPL = ₹33.77)

Meta ADS the Name of Growth Engine: A Case Study on Scaling Coaching Businesses in India

Off/On	Ad set	Budget	Last significant edit	Att. set	Results	Reach	Impressions	Cost per...	Amount spent	Ends	Schedule
<input type="checkbox"/>	Open	7...	218 Website leads	144,373	301,184	₹73.17 Per lead	₹15,951.43	Ongoing	5 Jun 2024-Ongoing
<input type="checkbox"/>	Englis...	7...	25 Website leads	17,692	25,604	₹50.97 Per lead	₹1,274.16	Ongoing	5 Jun 2024-Ongoing
	Results f	—	—	7...	243 Website leads	153,299 Accounts Centre accounts	326,788 Total	₹70.89 Per lead	₹17,225.59 Total Spent		

Appendix 4

Meta Ads Dashboard – Campaign Snapshot (₹17,225 Spend, 243 Leads, CPL = ₹70.89)

Off/On	Ad set	Budget	Last significant edit	Att. set	Results	Reach	Impressions	Cost per...	Amount spent	Ends	Schedule
<input type="checkbox"/>	Englis...	₹600.00 Daily	18 Nov 2024, 17:02 145 days ago	7...	3,178 Website leads	1,646,542	5,237,562	₹57.14 Per lead	₹181,593.46	Ongoing	19 Jan 2024-Ongoing
	Results f	—	—	7...	3,178 Website leads	1,646,542 Accounts Centre accounts	5,237,562 Total	₹57.14 Per lead	₹181,593.46 Total Spent		

Appendix 5

Meta Ads Dashboard – Campaign Snapshot (₹181,593 Spend, 3,178 Leads, CPL = ₹57.14)

Off/On	Ad set	Budget	Last significant edit	Att. set	Results	Reach	Impressions	Cost per...	Amount spent	Ends	Schedule
<input type="checkbox"/>	Englis...	₹375.00 Daily	...	7...	190 Meta leads	95,331	198,920	₹48.19 Per on-Face...	₹9,156.31	Ongoing	29 Dec 2023-Ongoing
	Results f	—	—	7...	190 On-Facebook leads	95,331 Accounts Centre accounts	198,920 Total	₹48.19 Per on-Face...	₹9,156.31 Total Spent		

Appendix 6

Meta Ads Dashboard – Campaign Snapshot (₹9,156 Spend, 190 Leads, CPL = ₹48.19)

Off/On	Campaign	Deliver	Actions	Bid strategy	Budget	Attribution setting	Results	Reach	Impressions	Cost per result	Amount spent	Ends
●	English coffe Le...	Off	---	Using ad set bid str...	Using ad set budget	7-day click...	3,178 Website leads	1,646,535	5,237,562	₹17.14 Per lead	₹181,593.46	Ongoing
●	C6 Gr Noida L...	Payment error	---	Using ad set bid str...	Using ad set budget	Multiple at...	2,270 Leads	682,734	1,814,755	₹82.98 Per Lead	₹63,504.78	Ongoing
●	C5 Noida 10/1...	Payment error	---	Using ad set bid str...	Using ad set budget	7-day click ...	931 Leads	270,391	517,331	₹63.77 Per Lead	₹31,442.74	Ongoing
●	C3 OPTIMIZE...	Off	---	Using ad set bid str...	Using ad set budget	7-day click...	177 Website leads	199,723	442,081	₹100.07 Per lead	₹17,712.18	Ongoing
●	(05/06) Noida L...	Off	---	Highest volume	₹415.00 Daily	7-day click...	243 Website leads	153,299	326,788	₹70.89 Per lead	₹17,225.59	Ongoing
●	C1 TEST Noi...	Off	---	Highest volume	₹813.00 Daily	7-day click...	123 Website leads	141,036	285,824	₹115.91 Per lead	₹14,257.15	Ongoing
●	C7 Online (24/0...	Off	---	Using ad set bid str...	Using ad set budget	7-day click ...	380 Meta leads	73,829	118,182	₹28.51 Per Meta lead	₹10,832.29	Ongoing
●	New Leads Ca...	Payment error	(1) 1 receive	Highest volume	₹500.00 Daily	7-day click ...	62 Meta leads	74,833	136,194	₹154.82 Per Meta lead	₹9,598.60	Ongoing
●	English coffe Le...	Off	---	Using ad set bid str...	Using ad set budget	7-day click ...	190 Meta leads	95,331	198,920	₹46.19 Per Meta lead	₹9,156.31	Ongoing
●	C4 Dynamic C...	Off	---	Using ad set bid str...	Using ad set budget	7-day click...	72 Website leads	121,028	182,873	₹104.24 Per lead	₹7,504.99	Ongoing
●	Retarget C2 C...	Off	---	Using ad set bid str...	Using ad set budget	7-day click ...	108 Website leads	54,053	81,124	₹54.74 Per lead	₹5,911.81	Ongoing
●	C8 IELTS (25/01...	Off	---	Using ad set bid str...	Using ad set budget	Multiple at...	17 Leads	61,136	93,736	₹282.26 Per Lead	₹4,798.40	Ongoing
●	Registration 11...	Off	---	Using ad set bid str...	Using ad set budget	7-day click...	64 Website leads	99,821	126,166	₹73.31 Per lead	₹4,691.82	Ongoing
●	(18/07/25) Noida Results from 28 c... Excludes deleted a...	Off	---	Highest volume	₹611.00	7-day click...	21 Multiple conversions	41,148	71,953	₹104.63 Total	₹14,671.44 Total Spent	Ongoing
							2,731,539	10,083,564	₹108.63	₹403,686.18		

Appendix 7

Meta Ads Dashboard – Consolidated View of All Campaigns (₹4,03,686 Total Spend, 8,085+ Leads, 2.7M Reach, 10M+ Impressions).

Author Biography

Srinjoy Ghosh is an MBA scholar in Digital Marketing Management at Amity University Online. His research interests include digital advertising effectiveness, social media marketing, and business scalability in the education sector. He is also actively working with coaching institutes in India to apply digital strategies for lead generation and growth.

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